

Deliverable 5.2

Documentation of community workshops

2025

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2025

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Executive Summary

This deliverable offers a synthesis of seventeen community-based workshops carried out within the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network. Framed under WP5 – Theorising Contested Territories: Generating alternative knowledge(s) – these initiatives were grounded in decolonial, creative and/or participatory approaches, aiming to explore and generate alternative forms of knowledge through processes which considered the active involvement of local communities across Europe and Latin America.

The workshops examined in this report address three critical dimensions of territorial contestation: the territoriality of politics, the dynamics of territorial accumulation, and the material and symbolic production of space. They span across a diversity of practices, including participatory design, collective mapping, intergenerational knowledge sharing, and creative practices. Going beyond traditional academic knowledge production, these activities have contributed to community empowerment, the redefinition of development paradigms, and the articulation of bottom-up territorial imaginaries.

This document follows and complements the Otros Saberes Toolkit (Deliverable 5.1), offering a grounded account of how contestation takes shape in practice. It underscores the methodological richness and political significance of workshops as spaces of collective learning, creation, and resistance in contexts marked by displacement, extractivism, and socio-political marginalization.

Introduction

Contested territories challenge the hegemonic way of producing knowledge by focusing the attention on the multiple ways in which people generate alternative understandings. This means to incorporate *otros saberes*, bottom-up processes of co-creation, and engaging in local practices that allows for collective creation and bottom-up processes of development. All these dimensions appear central to contest established power configurations and envision other ways to tackle the multiple issues affecting contemporary society and culture, going beyond and challenging expert knowledge. Entering into this collective endeavor implies developing encounters among communities and groups, in what we can generally refer to as workshops activities.

Currently, activities framed as ‘workshops’ have become a part of our everyday language, but have been weakly defined from an academic perspective, given their formats and uses developed within real-life contexts (workplaces, arts, politics). In common language, ‘workshop’ means an arrangement whereby a group of people learn, acquire new knowledge, perform creative problem-solving, or innovate in relation to a domain-specific issue (Ørngreen and Levinsen, 2017, p. 71). To recover its full potential to inform research, Mathews (2012, p. 349-350) suggests understanding ‘workshop’ as a time and space event for the undertaking of a particular kind of working together.

Workshops open a space for what can be called ‘natality’: an irreversible eruption of ‘newness’, without precedent and independent to human will. In this context they are understood as collaborative and creative acts to build knowledge. Following Ørngreen and Levinsen (2017), there are three types of workshops. In the first type, a workshop becomes a means to a specific end, that is, a type of knowledge is generated that has the potential to be directly transferred to practice and have an impact on reality. In the second type, they define ‘workshop’ as a practice through which an outcome is produced that serves participants as guidelines for future actions.

The third type implies using the workshop format as a research methodology to produce a specific research outcome in a certain domain.

In general, workshops are facilitated by experienced people to promote genuine participation by the active engagement of participants. The document Deliverable 5.1 – the *Otros Saberes Toolkit* – highlights twenty-four initiatives that have promoted *otros saberes* within the Contested Territories network, particularly those marginalized by hegemonic academic and policy frameworks, by recognizing the diverse ways in which they manifest.

This report is a follow-up of this first systematization. It revolves around the ways in which contestations acquired expression in concrete workshop settings. In this document, we will focus on workshops that have contributed to contestation in the three fields that guide Contested Territories:

- Contesting the territoriality of politics (public policies, modes of regulation and governmentality)
- Contesting territorial accumulation (by extended urbanization, displacement, extractivism, exploitation)
- Contesting the material and symbolic production of territories (by addressing the social production of inclusive habitat in bottom-up models of cultural, political and economic innovation).

In this document, we will examine seventeen workshop activities conducted during the project that cover a variety of fields of actions, including the strengthening of collective action, participatory design, methodological explorations, collaborative efforts with indigenous communities, and initiatives for social change. Rather than a formalistic synthesis, the effort is to characterize the ways in which individuals, society, and communities have come together to form a collective space to experience and understand territorial contestation. For each of the workshops considered, we offer a description of the purpose, the activities carried out, and a brief discussion of how contestations are expressed. At the end of this document, we look at the different modes of contestation we have encountered throughout the project.

Workshops

Workshop 1. Community Legal Promoters Program

Organizer

Asociación Civil por la Igualdad y la Justicia (ACIJ)

Participants

La Poderosa, Women's Houses, Latin American Justice and Gender Team (ELA)

Purpose

The "Community Legal Advocates Program" is a joint initiative of ACIJ's teams, which aim to strengthen the work of grassroots organizations through community legal empowerment actions.

This program seeks to enable these organizations to find in the law a tool to transform their realities. In this regard, we conducted training on rights and gender violence for gender advocates and residents of low-income neighborhoods who are part of various spaces of the Women's and Dissidence Houses that the organization La Poderosa maintains in several provinces of the country.

The initiative arose from a need for training in rights and gender violence. Its initial objective was to strengthen the mechanisms of the Women's Houses to accompany cases of violence, increasing and diversifying the range of legal tools and knowledge that allow for improving and making more efficient the accompaniment that is currently provided.

Date and place

During 2024 and 2025. Various workshops in Buenos Aires and Santiago del Estero

Activities

As part of the Community Legal Advocates Program, we held a total of five meetings with colleagues from La Poderosa, one of which was virtual and the rest on site. The virtual meeting was the first and was attended by 53 women from across the country. The aim of this space was to provide some basic concepts related to human rights, women's rights, and regulations on gender-based violence, as well as the Argentine judicial system.

This meeting was attended by the Latin American Justice and Gender Team (ELA), who provided information on regulations and the process for reporting cases of gender-based violence. Subsequently, we held in-person meetings in Buenos Aires and Santiago del Estero, considering that these places have a high incidence of violence cases.

Workshop: Community Legal Promoters Program, Santiago del Estero, Argentina, 2024

The first in-person meetings in both cities focused on assessing the cases or issues that the shelters deal with, as well as the challenges they face in supporting these cases and in their daily work.

The participants stated that this training would allow them to better understand the different processes they accompany and also to “empower” themselves and demand the fulfillment of their rights. Based on these first meetings, ACIJ developed a guide that aims to provide these tools, so that the Casas’ promoters can accompany cases of violence with greater knowledge and confidence.

The guide offers practical information on the process of reporting cases of domestic violence and the subsequent judicial proceedings, and also includes information on the legal framework regarding gender-based violence. The second face-to-face meetings in Buenos Aires and Santiago focused on presenting the information in the guide, reviewing its content together, and identifying any missing information or questions regarding the information included.

Contestation

As various authors have pointed out, gender-based violence is related to structural aspects of our society, linked to dimensions such as consumerism, materialism, and capitalism (Fuentes et al., 2016; Núñez, 2019). The promoter program allowed many women who are part of La Poderosa’s Women’s and Dissidence Houses to denaturalize situations of violence and understand that the state has an obligation to guarantee a life free of violence. The various meetings enabled these women to acquire legal knowledge and tools to address the situations of gender violence they experience and witness. All of the above is essential to strengthening the work and community fabric that has historically addressed this issue in neighborhoods, and is particularly relevant in the current context of defunding and dismantling of public policies aimed at preventing and eradicating gender-based violence. The work carried out increases the capacity for collective action, which is a central aspect in raising awareness and responding to this type of violence (Mulgan et al, 2011).

Workshop 2. Participatory architectural design in vulnerable sectors

Organizer

Universidad Nacional de San Martín

Participating nodes:

Basurama, Ciudades Reveladas, UNSAM

Purpose

Experience of participatory architectural practices in vulnerable territories aimed at building facilities and improving the habitat, following a working methodology based on listening and proactive reading. This involves generating a new matrix in relation to the conception of the discipline and the production of territorial knowledge, and also requires a high level of commitment to these territories and the populations that inhabit them.

Activities

Knowledge and academic activity were transferred to vulnerable territories by developing collaborative practices for the design of public facilities and infrastructure and habitat improvements in vulnerable areas of the municipality of San Martín, Argentina. The methodology is based on the fulfillment of three concepts that are developed at different times: the practice of listening, collective construction workshops, and the “co-evaluation” of public space. The processes of conversation, listening, and interpretation operate here as a project strategy and as a device for building trust and affection.

The development of these projects has a first stage of neighborhood tours, conversation, and public interviews, established as an exercise in knowledge that attempts a first approach to the issue and the problems to be solved, as well as understanding future projections and their limitations.

Date and place

2024-2025. The workshops have been held at the headquarters of the National University of San Martín, at the headquarters of social organizations in the participating neighborhoods, and at the Municipality of San Martín.

These exchanges have taken place in workshops that alternate between the headquarters of social organizations, the university, and the municipal offices.

The collective thinking exercise consists of interpreting everything heard in conversations with the community and the project's beneficiaries. Subsequently, it seeks to develop a plan that brings together the needs, physical and infrastructure requirements, possible growth, hypotheses of flexibility and transformation of spaces, and imagination about the maximum size of the project.

The “co-evaluation” of public space allows for an understanding that goes beyond the objective data from technical surveys, incorporating the perceptions and experiences of users.

Once these exchanges have taken place, the students produce a series of proposals that are presented at a public event, where the target audience shares their criticisms, opinions, and preferences. Everything that has been produced is then passed through a process of integration of all the ideas that have been highlighted, working with them in a collective exercise that synthesizes the program of needs and allows us to move on to the architectural and urban design stage.

Workshops carried out for the collaborative development of the public infrastructure project in the Merendero Rincón de Esperanza, Costa de Lago, San Martín, Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina. December 2024

Public presentation of the project to community members, Merendero Rincón de Esperanza, Costa de Lago, San Martín, Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina. March 2025.

Once these exchanges have taken place, the students produce a series of proposals that are presented at a public event, where the target audience shares their criticisms, opinions, and preferences. Everything that has been produced is then passed through a process of integration of all the ideas that have been highlighted, working with them in a collective exercise that synthesizes the program of needs and allows us to move on to the architectural and urban design stage.

At the end of this process, the first stage of the community facility is collectively built, with the participation of all the actors who have joined in throughout the process. This collective construction process must also generate the necessary consensus for its operational implementation in the territory, articulating the material resources and capacities of the different participating actors. In this last stage of these experiences, material praxis is understood as an essential component of the final adjustment of the project task and as the bearer of a specific body of ideas that allows for another type of learning.

Contestation

The work involves a new matrix of conception of the discipline and of territorial knowledge. This type of approach has an aesthetic impact of a political dimension, which entails a high level of commitment to the production of expectations that must not be disappointed, and which is directly immersed in the conditions and ways of life of people who face a future fraught with deficiencies of various kinds.

Participatory architecture challenges the architect-leader model, which is characterized by a type of management in which the architect unilaterally decides all aspects of the architecture and may or may not present them to the community for consideration (García, 2012, p. 5).

Workshop 3. Encounter Land and Housing

Organizer

Activity organized by the Frente de Organizaciones en Lucha (FOL), Argentina, which collaborated in gathering information from the tenant survey.

Participating nodes

CEUR- CONICET and IGEO-UBA

Purpose

To disseminate the results of the “tenant survey” and share knowledge about the rental housing market in working-class neighborhoods in the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area as well as tenements and boarding houses in the city of Buenos Aires.

Activities

The activity was part of the training sessions organized within a project called “Universidad Piquetera” (Squatter University). As part of the training, the organization invites different leaders from the academic and social spheres to share specific knowledge on topics related to urban extractivism, access to the city, territorial disputes, among other topics.

As part of the “Land and Housing” course, the organization invited members of the network to share the results of the Tenant Survey and exchange experiences and knowledge about the situation of tenant households in low-income neighborhoods, tenements, and boarding houses in the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area.

The main lesson learned is the importance of intersectoral coordination to generate knowledge about housing situations in low-income neighborhoods that remain invisible on the public agenda. Likewise, specific accounts of the experiences of those who live in territories that were not included in the survey were recovered. During the dialogues, it was recognized that coordination with social organizations is key to accessing these territories.

Date and place

November 2024, Faculty of Social Sciences, UBA

Workbook “Results of the Encuesta Inquilina” in the ‘Land and Housing’ course, Universidad Piquetera, organised by the Frente de Organizaciones en Lucha (FOL) at the Faculty of Social Sciences (FSOC-UBA). Credits: María de la Paz Toscani. November 2024.

Contestation

This experience provides an example of a response in which civil society organizations are not passive actors in the research process, but rather active agents who interpret and appropriate the data from the results of scientific research. From the perspective of participatory action research, unlike classical research, the relationship between the researcher and the researched subject is not one of subject to object, but rather one of subject to subject; people become protagonists of the research process and owners of the research results (Ander-Egg, 2003)

Workshop 4. Organizations and institutions of Family Farming

transformaciones territoriales, "Organizaciones e institucionalidad de la agricultura familiar".
 El mismo será dictado los días jueves 17 y viernes 18 de octubre, a las 9hs, en el aula 22 de la FHCSYS/UNSE por los docentes:
 -Carlos Cowan Ros (FAUBA-CEUR/CONICET)
 -Beatriz Nussbaumer (FAUBA-CONICET)
 -Dora Corvalán (Federación Provincial de Agricultura Familiar Tukuy Kusca)
 Ante cualquier duda o consulta, comunicarse por correo electrónico a: alytdiplomatura@gmail.com
 Les esperamos!
 Comparte esta noticia
 Interés General

Flyer promoting the workshop of the Diploma in Family Farming and Territorial Transformations, training proposal of the Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero

Purpose

The purpose of the workshop was to provide information on financing alternatives for the implementation of projects for family farming organizations and indigenous communities, aiming at building their capacity to identify the agenda and interests of financing agencies and compare them with their community priorities.

Activities

Over two days, training was provided in areas such as:

- national and international financing agencies
- financing agendas with a focus on the environment, more specifically the meaning and prioritization of environmental issues in financing lines
- analyzing the convergences and divergences between the ways in which issues are constructed in international and national financing agencies and the prioritization of those issues vis-à-vis the ways and conceptions of them in the organizations and communities of the participants

Date and place

 October 2024. Santiago del Estero, Argentina

Organizer

CONICET-CEUR

Participating nodes

CONICET-CEUR, UBA-AGRO

Participats

25 persons, including family farmers, rural workers, and members of indigenous communities in the province of Santiago del Estero, Argentina.

d) Alternatives for applying to different funding calls without altering the agendas, conceptions, and priorities of the organizations of the workshop participants.

e) Exercise on current and ongoing calls for proposals for the design of a project in line with the needs of rural communities in effective technical and administrative language with the logic of the funding institution.

Contestation

This form of contestation uses the channels of the current institutional framework to utilize the available instruments to advance contestatory agendas. In this way, workshop participants acquire the ability to reframe the ways in which environmental issues are constructed by funding agencies in accordance with the political projects of indigenous communities and organizations for the transformation of reality. In this form of contestation, collective organization is strengthened with the aim of innovating and meeting social needs (Mulgan et al. 2011).

Workshop 5. Observation and painting

Workshop Observation and Painting at the event Encounter with Water, November 2022

Purpose

To encourage group observation and imagination of the phenomenon of “water,” understanding it not as a material process existing in finite space, but recognizing the intrinsic power of water, since it penetrates our bodies and affects us. This workshop explores how water resonates in a reciprocal relationship within human beings and opens space to produce another type of knowledge through the artistic expression of shapes and colors.

Activities

The Observation and Painting workshop was part of the “Encounters with Water: Epistemological, Artistic, and Political Responses from Mallolafken” held between November 15 and 18, 2022. This meeting was inspired by the element of water as a way of making sense of the different responses that manifest themselves in the territory, with particular attention to other ways of producing knowledge. Participants in this event had the opportunity to enroll in a series of practical workshops that aimed to put the abstract deliberations we carried out in various conversations and discussion tables into practice and experience.

The workshop “Observation and Painting” sought to experiment with a methodology based on art and artistic expression to make the non-obvious obvious, see the unseen, and make the meaningless meaningful. To this end, the workshop begins with a reflective observation of the qualities of water, paying attention to how it manifests itself in different forms and is in continuous motion. This was followed by each participant's contemplative and imaginative inner immersion in the properties of water.

Date and place

November, 2022. Pucón, Chile

Organizer

Universidad de la Frontera

Participating nodes

Universidad de Sheffield, FLACSO, LeftHandRotation, Universidad de Leeds.

Finally, each participant developed a watercolor painting to reflect their inner experiences and capture the relationship that the individual develops with the natural world. The work concluded with a circle of reflective conversation sharing the results, a process that allowed for the emergence of new and vital collective knowledge.

Contestation

The workshop sought to move from a represented world to an experienced world through engaging with sensitivity and imagination. Painting was the modality selected to cultivate a relationship with nature in which the world of the senses and the human sensory organism change at the same time, in a relationship of reciprocity between humans and the natural world. This experience advances experimentation with embodied methodologies in which the sensitivity of bodies is intertwined with nature (Pink, 2010; Sabido, 2021, 2024).

Invitation for Encounters with Water at UFRU. Invitation design: Studio Sponja

Workshop 6. Song to Water: Perceptions and imaginations for a delta becoming

Workshop Song to Water at the event Territories in Times of Crisis, August, 2023

Purpose

This workshop explored how singing can become a form of knowledge.

Activities

The workshop Singing to Water: Perceptions and Imagination for a Delta Event was part of the conference "Territories in Crisis: Epistemological, Political, and Aesthetic Responses" held in Pucón between November 15 and 18, 2024. A central element of this meeting was to discuss and work with other methodologies. In particular, participants in the discussion "Political and Aesthetic Responses" shared the results of empirical work developed from methodological approaches informed by the body-territory perspective, human sensitivity, and the capacity for imagination. Each of the participants in this activity was invited to participate in the Canto al Agua workshop and to carry out a collective methodological exploration based on singing and inspired by the ethics of water.

To this end, they first worked on inner contemplation of the qualities of water and the development of different imaginations, understood as mental images produced within the human being when the qualities of water resonate. The singing gradually allowed different voices and different perspectives to come together in a collective song that reflects the emergence of shared knowledge. Based on the experience, a collective song was created that includes metaphors about the mysteries of the element of water and conveys ethical and political positions regarding the different territorial disputes that are manifesting themselves in southern Chile.

Date and place

August, 2023. Pucón- Chile

Organizer

Universidad de la Frontera

Participating nodes

UFRO, FLACSO-Ecuador

Contestation

This activity responds to the challenge of straining conventional modes of knowledge production by questioning the mind-body and society-nature separation characteristic of the Cartesian style of thinking inherited from classical European references. The activities developed in the workshop are inspired by recent proposals that endeavors in exploring the interstice between the human and the non-human, and that allow us to experience a plane of immanence that is formed from the intertwining of thought, feeling, and nature (Deleuze, 2007; Deleuze and Guattari, 1993). The song that gradually tunes into different voices is one of the ways to enter a creative-immanent plane that opens up different possibilities for the production of knowledge.

Event Territories in Times of Crisis, August, 2023

Workshop 7. Body bonding experiences

Workshop: Being Present Through the Senses, with Jose Vidal, Santiago 2024

Purpose

To promote a collective experience of bodily exploration through movement, play, and presence, in order to activate a sensitive and shared intelligence, recognizing the body as an agent of creation, transformation, and connection with the world.

Activities

This workshop was developed within the framework of “Encuentro Metodologías Otras; territorial disputes, dialogues, knowledge, and futures” held in Santiago between April 17 and 22, 2024. This meeting was conceived as a collective space for critical and creative exploration of unconventional ways of researching from, with, and in territories. Over the course of a week of activities, it brought together researchers, activists, artists, and communities around situated, creative, and collaborative methodological experiences. Through workshops, territorial tours, a project fair, and narrative exercises, it allowed for the sharing of findings, questions, and ways of doing research that challenge traditional forms of knowledge generation. In this context, the workshop “Experiencia de vinculación corporal” (Experience of Bodily Connection) was developed, facilitated by choreographer and director José Vidal, who proposed a space for collective bodily immersion through movement, play, and spontaneity. Far from understanding the body as a means of representation, the proposal situated the body as a sensitive, intelligent, and transformative territory, capable of activating memories, connections, and modes of knowledge that emerge in and from experience. Through dynamics of contact, shared attention, and creative overflow, the workshop enabled an embodied experience that allowed participants to experience a way of thinking and relating that does not begin with verbal language or abstraction, but rather with presence, gesture, and relationship with others. From the sensory and relational, the workshop fostered spaces for joint exploration, recognizing uncertainty, error, and

Date and place

18 April 2024. Espacio Matta Cultural Center. Santiago, Chile

Organizer

Universidad de Chile

Participating nodes

UFRO, Nodo Bolivia

From the sensory and relational, the workshop fostered spaces for joint exploration, recognizing uncertainty, error, and affectivity as fertile dimensions in creative processes. This space opened up the possibility of imagining and practicing other ways of narrating and transforming the processes we inhabit.

Contestation

The body is understood as an active place of perception, memory, and meaning, which reveals itself as a legitimate source of knowledge. From this perspective, the body not only feels or moves, but also knows and is capable of elaborating meanings through lived experience, gesture, and relationships with the world and with others. As Barbour (2016) argues, “embodied forms of knowledge” challenge the mind/body and knowledge/experience dualisms central to Western epistemology. This implies a revaluation of knowledge that emerges from sensation, movement, intuition, and affectivity, integrating dimensions that are often excluded in traditional academic methodologies. By proposing dynamics of presence, contact, and spontaneity, the workshop invited us to inhabit knowledge from another place: a porous, relational place, open to transformation, play, and creation. Here the body becomes listening, connection, and language, what Barbour (2016, p. 236) calls “an alternative epistemic strategy, where the somatic, the affective, the social, and the spiritual are not separate, but woven into the same gesture of knowing” unfolds.

Workshop: Being Present Through the Senses, with Jose Vidal, Santiago 2024

Workshop 8. International Meeting on Comparative Tenant Surveys

Organizer

IDRA (Barcelona Urban Research Institute)

Participating nodes

ACIJ, IDRA, HABITA65

Purpose

To analyze the results of the Tenant Survey and discuss issues related to the deregulation of the rental market, tenant insecurity, and inequalities in rental relationships in different cities (Barcelona, Madrid, Lisbon, Buenos Aires). In addition, policy proposals to improve the situation of tenants were explored.

Activities

Reports were reviewed and common and specific problems in the rental markets in Argentina, Spain, and Portugal were discussed. Preliminary proposals for future policies were also formulated. During the workshop, issues such as the lack of protection for tenants, economic pressure, and discrimination in access to housing were discussed. Participants identified the need to reorganize existing data and collect information on income and rent distribution to analyze the wealth gap between tenants and landlords. The experience promoted an exchange of experiences on the situation of tenants, highlighting the similarities and particularities in each context and emphasizing the importance of an international and comparative perspective in addressing housing issues.

Contestation

The workshop allowed participants to deepen their understanding of the dynamics of the rental market in different cities and the effects of deregulation on the daily lives of tenants.

Date and place

1st and 2nd July, 2024, Barcelona

International Meeting on Comparative Tenant Surveys (Day 2) - Credits: Monica Marion Cataño Otalora

International Meeting on Comparative Tenant Surveys (Day 2) - Credits: Monica Marion Cataño Otalora

Workshop 9. Contestations from Urban Peripheries: A Dialogue with Community Leaders from the Ecuadorian Amazon

Purpose

The workshop aimed to create a space for the exchange of experiences concerning the histories of struggle within the peripheral neighborhoods of the Ecuadorian Amazon. It brought together leaders from grassroots neighborhood organizations and researchers from the Contested Territories Network across the region, fostering dialogue and the sharing of experiences and resistance strategies within the Amazonian context.

Activities

The workshop opened with a roundtable session where all participants introduced themselves, presenting their community roles, research endeavors, and their motivations for attending the workshop. Following the introductions, a mapping exercise was conducted to trace the participants' trajectories, highlighting the importance of mobility in sharing lived experiences, grassroots activism, and the institutional representation of each participant.

Building on this activity, a community dialogue started with Marianita Jiménez and her daughter, Reyna Elisabet Gonzaga Jiménez, who presented the case of the Santa Marianita neighborhood in Lago Agrio (northern Ecuadorian Amazon). They discussed the everyday environmental hardships faced by families due to continuous exposure to oil flares and outlined the strategies developed through local and national social organization efforts to confront the environmental damages caused by oil extraction in the region.

The second session featured Digna Tenorio, leader of the 25 de Febrero neighborhood in Lago Agrio. The discussion focused on housing issues and the precarious living conditions exacerbated by environmental contamination linked to the expansion of oil infrastructure.

The dialogue emphasized the conflict between oil companies' efforts to expand extraction operations and community initiatives aimed at protecting environmental and social well-being. Key issues raised included the impact of flare explosions, oil spills, and the broader environmental degradation affecting residents' health and livelihoods.

Date and place

18 April 2024. Espacio Matta Cultural Center. Santiago, Chile

Organizer

Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO) Ecuador

Participating nodes

Universidad de La Frontera (Temuco); Universidad de Chile (Santiago); IIADI Bolivia.

Source

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2024

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2024

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2024

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2024

Following, Hernán Aguaiza, leader and president of the Luz y Vida neighborhood in Joya de los Sachas, presented a historical overview and analysis of the current challenges related to the legalization of the neighborhood, which is situated near an expanding oil platform. Three major issues were identified: soil and water contamination; social struggles characterized by collective neighborhood actions such as mingas (communal work) for the construction of a community center; and protest marches against pollution from oil flares.

Finally, Alexandra Knott, representative of the Cueva de los Tayos community and the Piatúa River Social Struggle in Pastaza, presented a case involving the lack of state provision of potable water and the problems caused by the flooding of the Pastaza River. She highlighted the state's prioritization of extractive projects, particularly the dam on the Piatúa River, which sparked widespread social mobilization in 2018 and continues to fuel collective resistance efforts. Additionally, she pointed out the challenges in education, particularly the erosion of bilingual education programs tailored to the community's cultural needs.

Contestation

The workshop provided valuable insights into the severe socio-environmental issues faced by communities as a result of extractive activities, as well as the broader environmental threats to which these communities are exposed. In terms of resistance, the discussions highlighted how local social organizations have initiated management efforts aimed at improving living conditions, seeking to establish connections with governmental bodies. Forms of resistance have been closely tied to the development of assemblies, public demonstrations, and social alliances, all of which have become central strategies in the ongoing struggle for territorial rights.

Workshop 10. Social Mapping of Risk and Vulnerability in the La Florida (Gran Colombia) Neighborhood, in the Amazonian City of Yantzaza, Ecuador

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2024

Purpose

The purpose was to develop a diagnostic tool for identifying perceived risks and the mitigation and/or adaptation strategies employed in the La Florida neighborhood, based on the individual and collective experiences of its residents. To achieve this, qualitative data collection was conducted, focusing on scenarios of residual urbanization and the social actors involved in urban production in the southern Ecuadorian Amazon region.

Activities

The workshop gathered 60 participants, including 55 adults (both women and men) and 5 children. The session began with a presentation by the research team from the Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization (OUA) and the Contested Territories Network, outlining the scope of their research projects and initiatives. This was followed by a welcome speech from the community, delivered by the neighborhood president. Subsequently, participants were divided into three working groups. The first group focused on the theme of risk perception, the second group addressed the construction of vulnerability, and the third group explored how children envision their neighborhood. Collective mapping exercises were conducted to spatialize risks, identifying key concerns such as fear of the Zamora River flooding and sweeping away residents and their belongings, the lack of a proper sewage system—raising fears of environmental contamination and increased disease—and the proliferation of alcohol sales and narcotic substances in the area.

Date and place

Yantzaza, Ecuador – November 20, 2024

Organizer

Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO) Ecuador

Participating nodes

Sheffield University, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) – Toulouse /Institut de Recherche pour le développement (IRD) – Paris, PUJ Cali.

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2024

Contestation

The workshop highlighted the critical risks faced by the community, including flood threats, recurrence patterns, and the most vulnerable areas, as well as the mitigation measures adopted by residents. The population perceives risk as closely linked to deficiencies in public services, notably the absence of a sewage system and the reliance on septic tanks, alongside growing insecurity, territorial fragmentation, and informality. Thus, contestation expresses itself in the creation of collective knowledge and action, involving children, youth, women, and the elderly.

Workshop 11. “Ñukanchik Kawsay”: Revitalization of the Kichwa Language with Children and Adolescents in the Parish of Pano, Napo, in Marginal Urban Contexts

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2025

Purpose

The objective of the workshop was to develop proposals for activities aimed at revitalizing the Kichwa language through collaborative methodologies involving young people.

Activities

The workshop brought together communities from the provinces of Sucumbíos, Orellana, Napo, and Pastaza. Kichwa is one of Ecuador’s 14 recognized indigenous languages. However, factors such as urban growth, migration, globalization, and the influence of mestizo culture have contributed to the gradual loss of these languages, particularly in urban areas where native languages are often stigmatized. In response, indigenous communities have promoted Intercultural Bilingual Community Education (ECIB), integrating languages such as Kichwa, Shuar, Achuar, and Wao Tededo into school curricula. Although several schools offer Kichwa language classes, they face challenges such as the lack of pedagogical materials, a shortage of bilingual teachers, and low motivation among children and adolescents to learn the language.

To address these issues, the workshop focused on engaging allies, volunteers, and facilitators to promote active use of indigenous languages among youth through innovative methodologies. The event began with an orientation session for teachers and authorities from the ECIB institution “El Pano.” Prior to the workshop, conversations were held with students, who shared their personal stories. Many revealed they were new to the school and had limited prior exposure to Kichwa.

Date and place

Sucumbíos, Ecuador | March 27, 2025

Organizer

Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales (FLACSO) Ecuador

Participating nodes

Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales (FLACSO) Ecuador

Source

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2025

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2025

Most students came from mestizo or indigenous families where Kichwa was spoken by older generations, particularly grandmothers. Although the students were not fluent speakers, they demonstrated a passive understanding of the language.

During the first phase of the workshop, students created body maps to illustrate the roles of Spanish and Kichwa in their daily lives. Some students reported knowing only a few words in Kichwa, while others indicated they retained the language in memory but did not perceive it as important. Their drawings reflected brief learning experiences and highlighted the coexistence of various forms of communication, including non-verbal communication, music, dance, and movement.

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2025

In the second session, it became apparent that for many students, it was their first time hearing a foreign language—Portuguese—as well as their first experience using Kichwa in more playful, non-academic settings. Activities like capoeira provided an informal space for students to engage with Kichwa beyond traditional grammar-focused instruction.

Contestation

The workshop highlighted the critical risks faced by the community, including flood threats, recurrence patterns, and the most vulnerable areas, as well as the mitigation measures adopted by residents. The population perceives risk as closely linked to deficiencies in public services, notably the absence of a sewage system and the reliance on septic tanks, alongside growing insecurity, territorial fragmentation, and informality. Thus, contestation expresses itself in the creation of collective knowledge and action, involving children, youth, women, and the elderly.

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2025

Observatory for Amazonian Urbanization, 2025

Workshop 12. Training Process on Gender and Environment in the Katari Basin

Dialogue session between members of the LHR Collective and other CT nodes with residents of the Katari Basin. Photography by IIADI, 2024.

Purpose

The objective of the workshop was to engage key stakeholders from communities affected by the Katari Basin, employing a gender-sensitive approach. The event created a space for reflection, dialogue, and collaboration, aimed at the collective development of solutions to address the pollution of the Katari River Basin and Lake Titicaca.

Activities

The workshop brought together a wide range of local actors from various areas across the basin, enabling the exchange of perspectives and experiences regarding the pollution challenges. Additionally, external experts contributed high-level technical knowledge and shared experiences from other cities worldwide that have faced similar environmental issues.

The first phase involved a mapping and diagnostic activity. This exercise identified the diverse realities, problems, and needs faced by the communities and municipalities within the basin. Following a general overview of the pollution context affecting the water bodies across the Katari Basin municipalities, the working methodology was introduced. Participants were divided into groups according to the sector of the basin in which they reside. They used a basin map and color-coded cards to record information related to flora and fauna, vital resources, social and cultural services, zones of pollution and environmental impact, as well as proposals and potential solutions.

Date and place

La Paz, Bolivia | February 2024

Organizer

Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI), supported by the Catholic Agency for Overseas Development (CAFOD)

Participating nodes

Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI); Polytechnic University of Milan; (Polimi) Left Hand Rotation Collective (LHR)

Dynamics on gender roles in urban and rural environments of the Katari Basin. Photography by IIADI, 2024.

The second phase focused on a gender workshop aimed at examining gender inequalities in the rural areas of the basin. This session helped highlight the impacts of pollution, alongside other challenges faced by the communities, and emphasized how these issues can disproportionately affect specific genders. The activity involved mapping the daily activities of men and women, differentiating the amount of time and schedules dedicated to daily tasks, and analyzing how these activities are disrupted by the effects of pollution and climate change.

The final phase consisted of a workshop to develop a coordination strategy among the various key actors within the basin to collaboratively formulate solutions to the socio-environmental problems. It is noteworthy that the development of these strategies was built upon extensive joint efforts between civil society organizations, governmental bodies, and, most importantly, the basin communities and institutions such as IIADI.

Contestation

The contestation processes focused on implementing actions aimed at holding accountable those responsible for the waste prevalent in the basin, including PET bottles and polystyrene. Efforts were made to influence these actors to support or initiate waste clean-up campaigns across the Katari Basin municipalities. The strategy involved delivering strong messages to those responsible, such as presenting them with contaminated water or community-generated waste, while documenting the entire process through audiovisual production.

A socialization strategy was developed, including the creation of a WhatsApp group comprising representatives from the Katari Basin and Lake Titicaca Defense Committee, affected communities (Alto Milluni, Puchukollo, Puente Seque, and Chojasivi), and strategic stakeholders. Additionally, a land restoration strategy was designed, integrating various knowledge systems and practices to rehabilitate land and water in areas experiencing severe environmental degradation. Finally, an education and clean-up strategy were established as a fundamental approach to addressing the socio-environmental challenges within the Katari Basin

Participatory mapping of environmental problems, resources; practices and activities in the Katari Basin. Photography by IIADI, 2024.

Group work between researchers from the University of Newcastle, Polytechnic University of Milan and community authorities from the Katari Basin. Photography by IIADI, 2024.

Group work between researcher from CEPLAG-UMSS and community actors from the Katari Basin. Photography by IIADI, 2024.

Workshop 13. Women, Science, and Innovation: Proposals and Actions for Managing Pollution in the Katari Basin and Lake Titicaca

Sharon Velásquez Orta – Chemical Engineer and Researcher, Newcastle University, 2025.

Purpose

The objective of this workshop-seminar was to create a space for sharing successful experiences, proposals, and innovations with a gender perspective. The event featured the participation of female presenters, government representatives, national and international researchers, and community leaders.

Activities

The workshop included a series of presentations focused on sharing and disseminating successful experiences. The first presentation was delivered by Sharon Velásquez, a researcher and associate professor in Sustainable Engineering at Newcastle University (United Kingdom). She addressed the transition from conventional remediation schemes to those with technological value, emphasizing the identification of characteristics of contaminated or wastewater. She presented the successful case of the Tula Valley project for treating wastewater from Mexico City, highlighting resource recovery from contaminated water and the use of microalgae. Following this, Karina González, a biologist specializing in Ecology and Conservation, presented cases of nature-based solutions applied to the Katari Basin, discussing challenges such as lack of financing and conflicts of interest. Verónica Amaru, from the Tiquipa community, Chojavisi Canton, Pucarani Municipality, presented on water management systems and distributed generation initiatives. Finally, Angélica Soroai, from the Directorate of Basic Sanitation, Water Resources, and Environmental Control of the Autonomous Municipal Government of El Alto (GAMEA), discussed the environmental policies and actions undertaken by GAMEA in the Katari Basin.

Date and place

El Alto, Bolivia | April 29, 2025

Organizer

Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI)

Participating nodes

Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI)

Eng. Karina González Pomar, Biologist – Hydroecology Specialist

Contestation

This seminar focused on learning processes through the analysis of successful cases in environmental protection and management, using as a reference the social and institutional initiatives currently being implemented in the Katari Basin.

Workshop 14. Territories in Contestation. Water Quality Assessment and the Development of an Environmental Agenda for the Preservation of Springs in La Paz, Bolivia

Colloquium held at the Museum of Anthropology and Folklore, August 16, 2022

Purpose

The objective of the workshops was to assess, through participatory processes and the methodology of knowledge dialogue (diálogo de saberes), the water quality of four springs located in the neighborhoods of Pasankeri, Kenanipata, Valle de las Flores, and San Antonio in the city of La Paz. Additionally, the workshops aimed to collaboratively develop an agenda for the protection, preservation, and appreciation of these springs as natural and cultural heritage, sustained by collective use practices and contesting forms of organization. The workshop adopted a social approach, examining local social practices such as communal laundry activities, diverse perspectives on the architecture of laundry facilities, and the social organization surrounding the stewardship of these spaces.

Activities

The workshops were designed with a focus on spring landscapes and an interdisciplinary perspective, recognizing that the landscape category enables the transcendence of the nature-culture dichotomy and encourages academic disciplines to move beyond their conceptual boundaries toward a more holistic understanding of reality (Dávalos, 2024). Throughout the workshops, analyses of the physicochemical and microbiological parameters of the spring waters were conducted, confirming the good quality of these water sources for various uses, including human consumption, in accordance with Bolivian Standard NB512 and World Health Organization guidelines.

Date and place

La Paz, Bolivia | August 2022

Organizer

Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI)

Participating nodes:

Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI)

Additionally, discussions were held regarding the management of water and land resources surrounding the springs and rivers, particularly engaging women involved in communal laundry work and urban agriculture. The workshops facilitated the connection between community-generated information on water quality and the exploration of socially and technically feasible reuse methods. Two community workshops were conducted with laundry workers at the four springs to collaboratively develop the environmental agenda. Finally, in coordination with the Institute for Research and Action for Integral Development (IIADI), the colloquium "Sustainable Management of Springs in Collective Laundries in La Paz" was held.

Contestation

As a result of these workshops, community mobilization efforts were strengthened to defend and revalorize these spaces in anticipation of potential future water crises, such as the one experienced in La Paz in 2016. The workshops contributed to the documentation of contested territories, the accumulation of territorial knowledge rooted in Indigenous traditions, and the co-production of sustainable resource management alternatives. Additionally, they fostered a dialogue of knowledge between natural sciences, social sciences, and community knowledge, culminating in the development of the Agenda for the Sustainable Management of Springs.

Workshop 15. Narratives and Memories of the Misak People: Toward the Co-Construction of a Living Memory Museum

Misak women drawing their territory. Photograph by Wilmer Camacho

Organizer

Pontifical Javeriana University of Cali (PUJ)
and Miskan Chak Association

Resources

PUJ / Ebert Foundation

Activities

As part of the ASC and Citizen Science project, the workshop began with an initial session centered on understanding community identity through a dialogue of knowledge (diálogo de saberes), fostering processes of collective learning. Subsequently, five workshops and three mingas (communal work gatherings) were organized within the community. The first workshop, titled the "Dreams Workshop," was followed by a social cartography exercise and a territorial tour to document the narratives and memories of the Misak People. The final workshop focused on the co-construction of objectives for the creation of a Living Memory Museum and the development of content for the museum. The mingas were dedicated to repairing the roofs of communal areas, patching walls, cleaning the surroundings, painting, and repairing the floors.

Date and place

Silvia, Colombia | 2023

Purpose

The aim of the workshop was to co-construct, together with Indigenous members of the Misak People, the living memory of taitas and mamas through a research and creative project. This initiative focused on recovering and preserving ancestral memory, highlighting the social, political, and identity struggles of the Indigenous community, and proposing a model of social and heritage museology.

Contestation

As an outcome of the workshop, a project titled Kampa Ya: Toward a Center of Living Memories for Peace was collectively developed. As well, The Kampa Ya Living Memory Center was open to public, featuring a photographic exhibition (Nupirau) and audiovisual productions. Contestation expresses itself in concrete collective action and knowledge production.

Workshop 16. Palenke Comunica

Mapping the Palenke, a cartography workshop

Purpose

Palenke Comunica is a communication initiative for social change developed through a collaboration between the El Palenke Community Council of El Hormiguero and the Pontifical Javeriana University of Cali. The project aimed to facilitate the exchange of knowledge and experiences between local youth and students from the Communication program at the university, under faculty supervision. Using a service-learning methodology, the initiative sought to promote community participation processes and contribute to strengthening the social fabric of the district. The main objectives were to create spaces for knowledge exchange and intersubjective experiences among young people, fostering mutual learning through communication practices, and ultimately providing a service to the El Hormiguero Community Council. Additionally, the project aimed to co-produce communication workshops to reinforce community cohesion by forming a core group of young peer educators and to co-design communication products that support the community processes undertaken by the Community Council of El Hormiguero.

Activities

Thirteen training workshops on leadership, communication, and content production were conducted with young people from the El Hormiguero district. Among these workshops were:

- Tejiéndonos Workshop, which focused on team building and collaborative co-production efforts to strengthen the community's social fabric;
- Tejido Workshop, an intergenerational activity involving children, youth, and adult women who collectively crafted bracelets, symbolizing the weaving of respectful, affectionate, and joyful relationships characteristic of the El Hormiguero community;

Date and place

March-November 2024.
El Hormiguero District and El Palenke Community Council

Organizer

Pontifical Javeriana University of Cali

Participating

Pontifical Javeriana University of Cali
El Palenke community council of the El Hormiguero district

- Designing in the Palenke Workshop, aimed at introducing youth to the use of artificial intelligence tools;
- Capturing El Hormiguero Workshop, a photography workshop designed as an example of knowledge exchange and mutual learning;
- Narrating Our Memory Workshop, where participants learned journalistic formats such as news articles, chronicles, and interviews.

Contestation

Community projects like Palenke Comunica strengthened bonds among the youth, which are essential for active participation, dialogue, and the expression of their ideas and concerns. These initiatives highlighted the importance of social development within and beyond the territory. The project enhanced communication skills among participants, enabling young people to feel heard and valued. Palenke Comunica has been a pedagogical, community-based, and participatory experience, allowing students to learn from and contribute to society through the lens of communication.

Voices of the Palenke, Podcast workshop

Workshop 17. Uma Kiwe, A Territory for All

Intercultural knitting workshop

Purpose

The purpose of this workshop was the co-creation of a proposal aimed at the reconciliation of the city's social fabric following the social uprising that took place in Colombia and was experienced with intensity and hardship in Cali on April 28, 2021.

Activities

The workshop began with the development of a "problem and solution tree," followed by a weaving workshop led by Nasa Indigenous women, and concluding with a poetry reading by a young Afro-descendant poet and rapper.

Uma Kiwe: A Territory for All was a co-creative research project that resulted in an exhibition involving four distinct population groups residing in Cali: Indigenous peoples from the Nasa community; young urban artists from the hillside neighborhoods of Commune 18; Afro-descendant communities; and socially marginalized youth, including university students from a private institution in the city. Together, the participants collaboratively constructed a "problem tree" to identify the critical issues affecting the city. They also proposed a symbolic reflection, expressed through art and communication, which was presented in the western part of Cali, one of the areas most severely affected during the national strike.

Uma Kiwe: A Territory for All is an artistic intervention that integrates photography, sound, audiovisual production, intercultural dialogue among Indigenous peoples, Afro-descendants, youth, and adults, and three collective and creative actions: one aimed at socially reweaving fractured ties in the city, a theatrical sketch recreating the situation of the national strike, and three rap performances articulating the experiences of social conflict. This visual, sonic, and creative work was exhibited at the Biblioteca del Centenario, located in the western sector of Cali, during its inauguration on December 2, 2021, and later at the library of the Pontifical Javeriana University on May 12, 2022. The project was curated by Professor María del Pilar Vergel.

Date and place

2022. Cali, Colombia

Organizer

Pontifical Javeriana University of Cali

Participating

Pontifical Javeriana University of Cali
Collective of ancestral weavers of life
Cypher neighborhood collective

The project was organized into two phases:

Chaos: The first phase commemorated the events of the national strike through images and a soundscape (photographs and ambient sound). A palabreo (dialogue session) was conducted with representatives from the various participant groups, including two Indigenous members, hip-hop artists, two university students, two Afro-descendant individuals, and two professionals—one from academia and one from the cultural sector. This phase also included a theatrical sketch based on a poem written by Mario Garcés, a young Afro-descendant, performed by actress Tatiana Donneys and accompanied by musician Camilo Corredor, who presented three original songs composed during the strike.

Integration: The second phase presented photographs and an audiovisual clip proposing narratives of integration, alongside performative actions. The first activity involved Indigenous women from the Nasa People, members of the Tejedoras Ancestrales de Vida Foundation, who invited attendees to participate in an onsite weaving activity, using threads in the colors of Cali's and Colombia's flags as a metaphor for rebuilding the social fabric. A second activity featured urban artists Cerve and Goofy, who performed their lyrics and engaged in freestyle rap. The objective was to transform the physical space into one of reconciliation and peace, embracing the challenges of integration and promoting respect for diversity.

Contestation

The initiative created spaces for reconciliation through embodied workshops, rap lyrics, reflections on the social uprising, photographic exhibition, conference presentation, and art gathering. These activities served to make visible the processes of community and social reconciliation.

Final Considerations

The work conducted under the workshop format allowed us to deepen our understanding of the different ways in which contestation takes shape in different contexts. We can distinguish three interrelated fields of action.

A number of activities were aimed at strengthening collective action in urban and rural settings by generating useful knowledge to respond to the multiple consequences of the developmental model implemented across the globe (for an account, see Brenner and Theodore, 2005; Morray, 2008). Workshops empowered people by providing legal tools and channels to address systemic violence (Community Legal Promoters) or by redefining problems to build platforms for the transformation of Indigenous and peasant communities (Family Farming). Collective action was also promoted by sharing research results and using them to support social demands and local political struggles (Land-housing, Tenant Survey).

Another group of activities takes the workshop format as a practice to construct shared knowledge that enables responses to the destructive consequences of current developmental trends from a community perspective. The activities fostered dialogue with local and indigenous communities who experience firsthand the effects of extractivism, rapid urbanization, and environmental degradation (Contestation from Urban Periphery, Social Mapping, Training Process, Women and Science, Water Quality). Workshops have also focused on building initiatives for social change through knowledge sharing and the rearticulation of the social fabric (Palenke Comunica, Uma Kiwe, aTerritory for All).

We can distinguish a third group of activities in which the workshop takes a methodological character aiming at generating knowledge in a particular domain. In an urban context, participatory and collaborative methodologies have been used to redefine professional practices, granting people due authority and agency to design their own habitat (Participatory Architectural Design). Moreover, the format has been put to work to explore other/alternative methodologies based on the body and human sensitivity, challenging traditional ways of knowledge production (Observation and Painting, Delta Becoming, Body Boding). We also highlight the collaborative work conducted with indigenous communities to revitalize the Kichwa language (Kickwa Revitalization) and to recover the ancestral memory (Narratives and Memories).

This brief overview of the workshop activities allows us to observe the variety of forms that contestation takes mainly in Latin America, ranging from pragmatic efforts aimed at building new grounds for collective action to epistemological explorations that destabilize conventional scientific approaches. We find initiatives that, from an academic standpoint, enter in dialogue with other forms of knowledge to raise alternative ways of development and resist current destructive trends. These threefold forms of contestation are indications of the efforts needed to foster coordination and dialogue among perspectives.

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contested

TERRITORIES

